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Research Portals (enhanced CRIS) as a source of Quality-controlled Metadata¹

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Introduction

Interconnecting open infrastructures is becoming a central task of the Open Science initiatives including those related to the dissemination of R&D information. The increasing use of PIDs (persistent identifiers), the development of new (very large) bibliometric databases with free API services and the implementation of NLP and AI techniques are allowing a more complete description of the activities and outputs of the scientific community.

However most of the automatic-based tasks are not able to correct basic errata, so many of the databases are incomplete and with a still high number of mistakes. Problems like disambiguation of author or institution names plagued the metric analysis even after the general, but far of being complete, adoption of identifiers (ORCID, RoR).

Human indexing is by far the best option, but it is time consuming and very expensive at global level. A feasible alternative is to be done at local level, involving directly the self-curation by the own people and organizations that are being indexed. Green Open Access promoted the development of a large number of institutional (and other) repositories (Ranking Web of Repositories <https://repositories.webometrics.info/>) that host probably more than 200 million records (CORE, BASE, OpenAIRE). Unfortunately, the IRs are very incomplete due to the restrictions of the commercial editors and the limited success of self-deposit, so institutions started to develop their own portals of research, researchers or CRIS (current research information system) for controlling and describing in one unique place all the outputs of their academic activities.

Although closely related and sometimes bridged, CRIS and IRs had been developed in parallel, being the first ones under the responsibility of the R&D Office, while the second is usually maintained by the Library.

Research Portals

There is no consensus in nomenclature, so we consider synonyms the research (or researcher) portal with the CRIS. Probably the first term refers more to a researcher-focused service, while the second one has a more institutional character. This is shown in the structure and the contents, but in fact the major differences are due to the characteristics and design of the software used.

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There are many different systems, some developed in-house while others are provided by companies that are leaders of the scholarly communication market, like for example Elsevier's PURE.

Contrary to IRs, many CRIS implementations are not public (as they are including sometimes internal delicate information) and the access is restricted only to the institution's personnel. That is a major issue for access relevant data but specially for sharing and interchanging information between different institutions. This attitude is against the open data principles and it is not looking justified by the limitations imposed by the personal data protection laws.

Nowadays, the diversity is the rule, not only regarding the organization and contents, but especially considering the type and standards of metadata and metrics used.

Objectives

The aim of this contribution is to provide a description of the services, metadata and metrics provided by a group of CRIS that uses different software in order to identify main trends, major information sources, and limitations and shortcomings of these services. The focus is on information that can be used for metrics-based studies.

Methods

We selected 10 institutional CRIS representing each one different software platforms (Table 1). All revised institutions are Universities: 5 from Spain, and one each from Hong Kong (PRC), India, Italy, Poland and Chile. Two of them are in-house developments while the others are products with several implementations. There is a comprehensive list of CRIS classified by the software they are using in the Directory DRIS (<https://dspacecris.eurocris.org/cris/explore/dris>)

Table 1. CRIS names and addresses with indication of the implemented software.

SOFTWARE	EXAMPLE	URL
DSpace-CRIS	accedaCRIS Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	<i>accedacris.ulpgc.es</i>
IN-HOUSE	HKU Scholars Hub University of Hong Kong	<i>hub.hku.hk</i>
Omega-PSIR	Base of Knowledge Warsaw University of Technology	<i>repo.pw.edu.pl</i>
PURE	Portal de Investigadores Universidad Andrés Bello	<i>researchers.unab.cl</i>
iMARINA	Portal científico Universidad Autónoma de Madrid	<i>portalcientifico.uam.es</i>
Dialnet CRIS	Portal de la investigación Universidad de la Rioja	<i>investigacion.unirioja.es</i>
VIVO	Universidad Carlos III de Madrid Research Portal	<i>researchportal.uc3m.es</i>
IN-HOUSE	FUTUR Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya	<i>futur.upc.edu</i>
IRINS	Indian Institute of Technology Bombay Faculty Profiles	<i>iitb.irins.org</i>
IRIS	IRIS Sapienza Università di Roma	<i>iris.uniroma1.it</i>

The portals were manually checked for a series of characteristics during March and April 2022. A preliminary analysis was presented at the 8th Seminar of University Knowledge Bases (<https://conference.omegapsir.io/>)

Results

We started describing quantitatively the contents of the websites according to external sources. In some cases, the CRIS is also the repository (IR), combining both roles. The size (number of

webpages) and number of pdf (adobe acrobat) files were obtained from Google (April 4th, 2022) using the operators' site and filetype. The number of records indexed by Google Scholar were obtained on the same date using the syntax site:xxx.yy.

Table 2. CRIS size according to Google (number of webpages and pdf files) and Google Scholar (umber of primary items indexed). April 2022

CRIS	REPOSITORY	SIZE	PDF	SCHOLAR
<i>accedacris.ulpgc.es</i>	YES	161000	23100	17600
<i>hub.hku.hk</i>	YES	177000	38900	0
<i>repo.pw.edu.pl</i>	YES	107000	6830	39200
<i>researchers.unab.cl</i>	DOI	33200	52	302
<i>portalcientifico.uam.es</i>	DOI	12600	1	0
<i>investigacion.unirioja.es</i>	YES	38800	727	946
<i>researchportal.uc3m.es</i>	NO	28900	1	0
<i>futur.upc.edu</i>	LINK TO IR	117000	0	0
<i>iitb.irins.org</i>	DOI	738	0	0
<i>iris.uniroma1.it</i>	YES	38500	30300	3990

The Google size is probably correlated to the number of the scholars of the university, although the diversity and structure of the individual entries are also playing a role. However, the number of pdf files are clearly larger when CRIS is also the IR (ULPGC, HKU, UNIROMA1). On the contrary the bibliographic records without full text documents can be large according to Google, but not by Google Scholar. It looks the HKU Scholars Hub is not indexed by GS, perhaps because it is not recognised as repository or by an unknown technical reason that make difficult the indexing of its contents.

Table 3. Public information provided by the CRIS for each individual. April 2022

CRIS	PERSONAL INFO	NARRATIVE	EXPERTISE	EXPERIENCE	EDUCATION	AWARDS
<i>ULPGC</i>	CONTACT/DEPT-GROUP/IdD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
<i>HKU</i>	CONTACT/DEPT-GROUP/IDs	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
<i>PW</i>	CONTACT/DEPT-GROUP/IDs	NO	WORD CLOUD	YES	NO	YES
<i>UNAB</i>	NO	NO	TOPICS	NO	NO	NO
<i>UAM</i>	CONTACT/DEPT-GROUP/IDs	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO
<i>UNIRIOJA</i>	CONTACT/DEPT-GROUP/IDs	YES	(YES)	(YES)	(YES)	(YES)
<i>UC3M</i>	CONTACT/DEPT-GROUP/IDs	NO	NO	(YES)	NO	NO
<i>UPC</i>	CONTACT/DEPT-GROUP/IDs	NO	YES	NO	NO	(NO)
<i>IITB</i>	GENRE/CONTACT/IDs	NO	TOPICS	YES	YES	YES
<i>UNIROMA1</i>	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO

According to the Table 3 data, there are two CRIS software (Italian IRIS and the public PURE) that do not provide a lot of personal and context information about the individual researchers. The other designs are very different among them, both regarding the quantity and diversity of the information provided. Except by the narrative (mostly an executive summary of the CV)

the number of metadata fields is very limited and the contents usually not following any standards. In some cases, this is mostly due to the different countries traditions for describing positions and degrees.

Far more relevant is the data regarding the outputs, as it is mostly quantitative. In the Table 4 we included the information about the Open Access status of the documents described. In spite most of the CRIS indicate if a paper is or not OA, only one identifies the OA type (color).

As expected, there is a lot of metrics, including the number of documents classified by type, and in couple of CRIS there is an attempt to organize them by the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) involved or related to. Regarding the numbers, we can notice what are the sources of this bibliographic information, as the (intended) complete local production is placed in context with the data from the commercial bibliometric databases (mostly WoS and/or Scopus). But, although usually the figures are comprehensive, in others cases non-matching documents are excluded. Open data (datasets) are included in some CRIS, but the coverage is still limited. On the contrary, the own or directed thesis, patents and projects receive a full coverage. Additionally, in many cases the CRIS editors are especially interested in providing nice graphs showing the co-authorship relationships among authors.

Table 4. Types of individual outputs included in the analysed CRIS. April 2022

CRIS	OUTPUT	OA INFO	PATENTS	THESIS	DATA	PROJECTS	COOPERATION
<i>ULPGC</i>	PUBLICATIONS (BY TYPE)	YES	YES	YES	()	YES	CO-AUTHOR NETWORK
<i>HKU</i>	SCOPUS / WoS / PubMed / CiteULike/F1000	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	CO-AUTHOR LIST & NETWORK
<i>PW</i>	PUBLICATIONS (BY TYPE/SDG)	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	CO-AUTHOR NETWORK
<i>UNAB</i>	PUBLICATIONS (BY TYPE/SDG)	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	CO-AUTHOR MAP
<i>UAM</i>	WoS/SCOPUS	YES	YES	YES	()	YES	CO-AUTHOR NETWORK
<i>UNIRIOJA</i>	PUBLICATIONS (BY TYPE)	YES	NO	YES	NO	YES	LIST OF CO-AUTHORS/ORGS
<i>UC3M</i>	PUBLICATIONS (BY TYPE)	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	CO-AUTHOR NETWORK
<i>UPC</i>	PUBLICATIONS (BY TYPE)	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	CO-AUTHOR NETWORK
<i>IITB</i>	PUBLICATIONS	BY COLORS	YES	NO	()	NO	CO-AUTHOR NETWORK
<i>UNIROMA1</i>	PUBLICATIONS (BY TYPE)	YES	()	NO	NO	NO	NO

Although core to most of the CRIS analysed, the metrics section is sometimes very confusing. There are metrics in the front page of each profile, but they can appear also differently and independently in other sections. So, for example, the article-level variables are sometimes hidden in the list of publications, terminology is not standardised and in the case of Omega-PSIR, the system is even using incorrect metrics (global Impact Factor and Citescore). The Table 5 clearly shows the duopoly WoS/Scopus as the main metrics providers, although

altmetrics (Altmetric.com and PlumX) are used in many cases. Google Scholar, Dimensions or CrossRef are also used in a few CRIS.

Table 5. Types of metrics and sources used in the analysed CRIS. (WoS=Web of Science, SC=Scopus, GS=Google Scholar, PBL=Publons, DIM=Dimensions, PUBM=PubMed, CR=CrossRef). April 2022

CRIS	CITATIONS	H INDEX	ALM	JLM	ALTMETRICS
<i>ULPGC</i>	NO	NO	NO	JCR Q	()
<i>HKU</i>	SC	SC	ALTMETRIC	NO	YES
<i>PW</i>	GS/WoS/SC	GS/WoS/SC	WoS/SC	WoS/SC	PLUMX
<i>UNAB</i>	SC	SC	SC	NO	PLUMX/ALTM
<i>UAM</i>	WoS/SC/GS/PBL	WoS/SC/GS/PBL	DIM/WoS/SC/PUBM	WoS/SC	NO
<i>UNIRIOJA</i>	NO	NO	ALTMETRIC/PLUMX	NO	NO
<i>UC3M</i>	NO	NO	PLUMX	NO	PLUMX
<i>UPC</i>	NO	NO	SC/GS/ALTMETRIC	NO	ALTMETRIC
<i>IITB</i>	SC/CR	SC	DIM/SC/SCITE/CR	NO	SEVERAL
<i>UNIROMA1</i>	NO	NO	PMC/WOS/SCOP	NO	PLUMX

Finally, we made a webometric analysis of the mentions to the URLs of the selected CRIS in the main social tools (Table 6). We counted the number of times these URLs appear in the websites of the social services.

As it can be expected the two CRIS with repository attached are the most frequently mentioned in the academic networks, as the target of both Academia and ResearchGate are both the profiles and the documents.

CRIS contents are probably too sophisticated to general public so tools like Facebook or LinkedIn are not mentioning them. As there is no Russian or Chinese CRIS in our sample, their national social tools are ignoring the services analysed by us.

We have included several specialised deposits, like those hosting presentations, software or datasets. Again, the perceived correlation with those CRIS-with repository services attached, although the number are pretty low.

Perhaps the most interesting ones are the mentions in the Wikipedia editions. The number of researchers with an individual entry in Wikipedia is increasing, so you can expect the CRIS profile could be mentioned in such article. Obviously only top researchers usually deserve the entries, but even after considering that the numbers are very low. The outlier is the Hong Kong University CRIS that is titled as “Scholars Hub”, an in-house design that focus on the individuals.

The figures are also very low for YouTube, Instagram and Zhihu, probably because they cover contents still not being well indexed in the current generation of CRIS. However, it can be expected that Twitter will be more popular for distributing information about news regarding the CRIS. Probably academic community managers still do not consider CRIS as a visibility tool, but mainly as a source for internal management.

Discussion

We described a tool (research portal/CRIS) that, although designed for bureaucratic control, it is providing a valuable source of metadata information about the research activities and outputs of the institutions. The fact that is built and revised locally can be a guaranty of human quality curation that could be better than the one supplied by the commercial indexes. The results show that there is a lot of CRIS services that need to be polished, that most of the metrics still came from traditional external sources (duopoly WoS/Scopus) and that there is little standardization (in spite of CERIF) for exchanging data except if there are sharing the same CRIS software.

However, the number of CRIS installed are growing fast, many became public and the new generations of software are providing richer and better interfaces. Moreover, the open APIs from the new bibliometric databases (Dimensions, OpenAlex, Semantic Scholar, Lens) can add more quantitative information to outputs not indexed by WoS/Scopus. This includes new relative indicators that are far more useful for evaluation purposes.

This contribution is a plea to both the metric community to pay more attention to CRIS as a source of valuable local curated information and to the CRIS developers and their customers in the academia for increasing the quantity and quality of the metadata incorporated in the new versions of their programs.

Table 6. Mentions of the URLs of the analysed CRIS in selected social networks. April 2022

GROUP	TOOLS	ULPGC	UPC	HKU	IITB	UNIRIOJA	UNIROMA	UAM	PW	UNAB	UC3M
ACADEMIC	RESEARCHGATE	1460	129	5830	1	51	1930	2	83	6	3
	ACADEMIA	52	42	675	0	6	41	5	8	4	2
GENERALS	FACEBOOK	282	33	256	1	5	52	1	24	1	0
	LINKEDIN	8	93	49	0	2	9	5	38	6	6
	VK	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
	WEIBO	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
(DATA)	SCRIBD	457	142	210	0	2	7	5	2	4	3
DEPOSITS	SLIDESHARE	13	36	75	0	0	2	3	2	0	1
	GITHUB	0	2	49	0	0	3	0	3	0	0
	FIGSHARE	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	ZENODO	5	0	15	0	0	7	0	0	0	0
	SOURCEFORGE	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	57	0	0
	DATAVERSE	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
WIKIPEDIA	WIKIPEDIA	5	1	98	0	1	8	20	3	0	2
	WIKIPEDIA (ENGLISH)	1	0	41	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
(MICRO/MEDIA)	TWITTER	186	200	185	0	47	62	5	5	54	8
BLOGS	YOUTUBE	9	5	7	0	0	3	1	2	1	0
	INSTAGRAM	0	3	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
	ZHIHU	0	0	67	0	0	0	0	0	0	0